

Studies on the Stability and Electrokinetic Potential of Ceric Oxide Sol

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Positively charged ceric hydroxide sol has been prepared by dialysing a 3% ceric ammonium nitrate solution. The following equation connecting ζ with ζ_a has been found to hold good both for rapid and slow rates of coagulation:

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + m \cdot \frac{1}{S}$$

where ζ_a represents apparent zeta-potential calculated from the Smoluchowski equation, S , the specific conductance of the solution of an electrolyte at its equicoagulating concentration, ζ , the true zeta-potential, and m , a constant under the conditions of the experiments.

The electrolytes used for coagulation are: NaCl, Na₂SO₄, K₃FeCy₆, and mixtures of NaCl and Na₂SO₄ and NaCl and K₃FeCy₆.

The values of ζ (true zeta-potential) found from (Fig. 1) are 25.6 mv and 26.7 mv for rapid and slow rates of coagulation respectively.

It has been shown by Ghosh and co-workers (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, 49, 1477; *Science & Culture*, 1954, 18, 489; this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 274, 393) that the true zeta-potential, ζ , of colloidal particles in presence of equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes containing counter ions of different valencies can be found by using the equation,

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + m \cdot \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where ζ_a represents the apparent potential calculated from electro-osmotic data by the Smoluchowski equation, S is the specific conductance of the solution in equilibrium with the colloidal particles, and m is a constant under the conditions of the experiments. For electro-osmosis

$$m = \frac{3V_1X}{\zeta V_2R}$$

where V_1 and V_2 represent the volume of the solid and solution respectively in the diaphragm, R is the radius of the colloidal particles, and X , sp. surface conductance.

These authors have also concluded from their results that a given rate of coagulation of a colloid is characterised by a definite value of the true zeta-potential independent of the valency of the counter ions used. With a view to ascertaining the applicability of the theories advanced by those authors, experiments have been undertaken with ceric oxide sol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Colloid.—Positively charged ceric oxide hydrosol was prepared by the dialysis of a solution of ceric ammonium nitrate (Blitz, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4431; *Z. anorg.*

Chem., 1927, 198, 93). A 3% solution was allowed to stand for five days, when a slightly turbid, greenish yellow sol resulted. This was first electro-dialysed for 12 to 15 hours and then dialysed in cellophane bags for about 3 weeks. Its ceric oxide content was 0.5% and the specific conductance was 1.421×10^{-4} mhos at 25°.

Determination of the Equicoagulating Concentration.— A given volume of electrolyte (2 c.c.) was mixed with an equal volume of the sol and the mixture was left as such for 10 minutes or 20 hours for rapid or slow rates of coagulation respectively. The mixture was centrifuged afterwards for 2 minutes at a definite speed and the supernatant solution was examined for transparency or opacity. The concentration of the electrolyte, which just gave a transparent supernatant solution, was taken as the equicoagulating concentration. The electrolytes used for rapid and slow rates of coagulation were: NaCl, Na_2SO_4 , K_3FeCy_6 , and mixtures of NaCl and Na_2SO_4 and of NaCl and K_3FeCy_6 .

Electro-osmotic Experiments

The electro-osmotic experiments were carried out at 25° by Bredig's method in the U-tube apparatus as described by Mukherjee *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1927, 4, 493). A definite volume of the electrolyte solution was mixed with an equal volume of the colloid so that the final concentration of the electrolyte in the mixture represented its coagulating concentration. The mixture was allowed to stand for 10 minutes or 20 hours according as the rate of coagulation was rapid or slow. The coagula were then separated from the supernatant liquid by centrifuging and were transferred to a U-tube. The U-tube containing the coagula was next centrifuged so that the coagula occupied a definite volume in each of the experiments, thereby securing the constancy of V_1 and V_2 as required by equation (1). R can be assumed constant since the coagulation procedure was closely standardised. Centrifugate was used for the supernatant liquid and its specific conductance was determined.

The velocity of electro-osmotic flow was measured from the rate of movement of the air bubble. The current passing through the diaphragm was noted and the values of ζ_a were calculated from the Smoluchowski equation. The reproducibility of the electro-osmotic data was found to be within $\pm 3\%$.

The extrapolated values of the true zeta-potential of ceric hydroxide sol in the region of rapid and slow rates of coagulation were found to be 25.6 mv and 26.7 mv.

The values of $1/\zeta_a$ were plotted against the corresponding values of $1/S$ in Fig. 1 in which the straight line (I) represents rapid and the line (II), slow coagulation respectively.

DISCUSSION

In the zone of rapid coagulation the values of ζ_a found for different electrolytes vary from 12.4 to 24.8 mv, but they satisfy the linear relationship as required by equation (1).

For slow coagulation the values of ζ_a found for different electrolytes vary from 15.5 to 25.4 mv. The plot of the values of $1/\zeta_a$ against the corresponding value of $1/S$ yields, however, a straight line as required by equation (1).

At the equicoagulating concentrations of the electrolytes and their mixtures, under the conditions of our experiments, ζ and m therefore remain constant. The values of ζ and m , found from the intercept and the slope of the straight line (I) for rapid coagulation, are 25.6 mv and 6.872×10^{-3} respectively.

FIG. 1

The experimental results also lead to the conclusion that a given rate of coagulation of the ceric oxide sol by the electrolytes used is characterised by a definite value of true zeta-potential, independent of the valency of the counter ions used.

The author expresses his grateful thanks to the C.S.I.R. for a research fellowship.